

Design and Testing of Sensor Configurations for a Wearable System to Assess Bradykinesia and Tremor in Parkinson's Disease

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Abstract— Bradykinesia is a key symptom of Parkinson's disease, characterized by slowed initiation and execution of movement, along with reduced range and rhythm. Tremor is another well-known Parkinson's disease symptom, most noticeable in the hands. This study, part of an internship project, aimed to develop and evaluate optimal placements for Electromyography (EMG) and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors on a wearable glove to objectively assess bradykinesia in Parkinson's disease. The first author performed four hand movement tasks, Finger Tapping, Hand Movement, Flexion and Extension, and Pronation and Supination, under three simulated conditions: Healthy, Bradykinesia, and Tremor. EMG electrodes were placed on specific hand muscles, while IMU sensors were positioned on the wrist. Data processing and feature extraction were performed in R. Results indicated that the proposed sensor configuration effectively captured relevant signals, allowing accurate movement detection across all three conditions.

Keywords — Parkinson's disease, Electromyography, Inertial measure units, Wearable sensors, Bradykinesia.

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a chronic neurodegenerative disease that affects the central nervous system. It results from a progressive degeneration of dopaminergic neurons located in the substantia nigra, leading to a significant decrease in dopamine, a neurotransmitter essential for motor control [1, 2].

Motor symptoms such as resting tremors, muscle rigidity, postural instability, and bradykinesia are the most common clinical manifestations of Parkinson's disease (PD). Among these, bradykinesia, defined as the slowness in the initiation and execution of movement, accompanied by a reduced range of motion, is considered the hallmark symptom of the disease [3]. Tremor, another primary motor symptom of PD, is characterized by considerable phenomenological heterogeneity, including variability in frequency, amplitude, and anatomical distribution [4]. Both bradykinesia and tremor significantly impact quality of life by limiting mobility and increasing a sense of insecurity during routine tasks.

Therefore, it is essential to be able to accurately assess bradykinesia and tremor in Parkinson's disease, with the aim of improving the clinical monitoring of patients, the adaptation of their treatments, as well as the development of

new therapeutic interventions.

The follow up of PD is based on the assessment of motor and non-motor symptoms, usually during clinical examinations using subjective scales such as Hoehn and Yarn (H&Y) and the Movement Disorder Society Unified Parkinson's Disease Rating Scale (MDS-UPDRS). However, these methods remain suboptimal for the management of PD, especially when factors such as advanced age, impaired cognitive functions or reduced mobility intervene [3, 5].

In this context, the use of smart technologies for PD-related applications has increased in recent years. Wearable sensors play a fundamental role in helping neurologists to perform objective quantification of symptoms over time. A growing number of studies published in the last decade demonstrate the development and increased use of these wearable technologies [6–8]. For example, the use of inertial sensors such as accelerometers and gyroscopes, combined with communication technologies like Bluetooth, now meets the needs of people with chronic disorders. This is possible thanks to their low energy consumption, discreteness, lightness, and ease of use [7].

This study is a part of an internship project that aimed to develop a personalized glove that allows to objective assess bradykinesia and detect tremor in Parkinson's disease. Considering that the electromyography (EMG) is a valuable tool to assess alterations in muscle activation patterns that accompany bradykinesia, and that the inertial sensor (IMU) is a stablish technology to detect motion, the device should combine EMG electrodes and inertial sensors (IMU). The glove must be able to collect relevant data on muscle activity and motion.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to propose and test optimal sensor placements for Electromyography (EMG) and Inertial Measurement Unit sensors for a wearable glove, and to evaluate their effectiveness in detecting bradykinesia and tremor symptoms during hand movement tasks.

II. METHODS

A. Data collection

Volunteer: One researcher performed the tasks, executing each one three times under different conditions: Healthy (normal movement), Bradykinesia (slower movements with

reduced amplitude and rhythm), and Tremor (movements with simulated tremors).

Tasks: In clinical practice, to test bradykinesia on the upper limbs, clinicians use Part III, the motor examination of the MDS-UPDRS. In some specific items, they ask the patient to perform rapid alternating movements. It is important to remember that these movements should be performed as quickly as possible and as widely as possible, that is, with the greatest possible amplitude. All these tests are positive for bradykinesia if the amplitude of movements and/or speed decrease over time.

Based on this information, three items related to bradykinesia on the hands were included in the protocol, finger tapping, corresponding to MDS-UPDRS item 3.4 (tapping index finger on thumb), hand movement, corresponding to item 3.5 of the MDS-UPDRS (to open and close the hand), and pronation and supination, corresponding to point 3.6 of the MDS-UPDRS. Besides these tasks, wrist flexion and extension were also included because it is considered an important movement to measure bradykinesia [3].

Technology: For EMG collection, Meditrace Ag/AgCl electrodes were used, 36 mm in diameter, 2 per muscle allowing bipolar recording (using two electrodes (+,-)), to capture the potential differences between the most distant electrodes and thus minimizing the noise recorded on a single electrode. The setup for data collection had a regulated DC power supply (INSTRUTHERM, model FA-3050), a 16-channel biological signal acquisition system (SASBio, a device developed from the technology of INTAN TECH's RHD2000 evaluation system) coupled with the RHD2000 graphical interface software and a sealed battery (C-3329, 12 V, 7A).

For IMU collection, the system NetMD was used. NetMD is a movement disorder monitoring system able to remotely and continuously analyze and monitor movement disorders using inertial signals. The system is based on the joint action of an Android mobile phone and smartwatches (Sony, Smartwatch3, model SWR50), with communication established via Bluetooth. This system allows the acquisition of signals from the internal gyroscopes and accelerometers of the smartwatch, with a sampling frequency of 50 Hz (i.e. with a temporal resolution of 20 ms). Data is subsequently transferred to the mobile phone and stored internally in a compressed file (txt). These sensors are sensitive to acceleration and angular velocity, which makes it possible to track almost all human physical activity in three dimensions [7].

Positioning of sensors: To assess bradykinesia and tremor during the various defined motor tasks, precise positioning of EMG and IMU sensors is necessary. The choice of target muscles and sensors is optimized to ensure high signal quality and relevance to the movements studied. The EMG sensors were placed on the First Dorsal Interosseous (FDI), Flexor Pollicis Longus (FPL), and Flexor Digitorum Profundus (FDP) muscles on the right side of the body. And the smartwatch with the inertial sensors was on the wrist, as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1 shows two electrodes on the FDP, two on the FPL, two on the FDI and one on the ankle bone

(reference electrode, shared for all muscles).

B. Data preprocessing

For the EMG data, a multi-step filtering process was applied to eliminate noise and isolate biologically relevant frequency bands. To remove low-frequency artifacts like cable movement noise, a 4th-order Butterworth high-pass filter with a 0.02 Hz cutoff was used. High-frequency noise was reduced using a 4th-order Butterworth low-pass filter with a 0.5 Hz cutoff (for 500 Hz sampling rate). Additionally, a 60 Hz Butterworth notch filter was implemented to eliminate power line interference common in regions like Brazil.

Fig. 1. Sensor's placement. The electrodes of EMG on the Flexor Digitorum Profundus, Flexor Pollicis Longus, First Dorsal Interosseous. The IMU sensors on the wrist.

For the IMU data (accelerometer and gyroscope), both linear (DC offset) and nonlinear trends were removed. The DC offset was corrected by subtracting the signal mean. Then, a 4th-order Butterworth high-pass filter with a 0.5 Hz cutoff (sampling at 100 Hz) was applied to remove low-frequency trends.

To further refine the IMU signals, Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) was used. EMD decomposes non-stationary, nonlinear signals into Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs), which isolate specific oscillatory modes. Noise-related IMFs were discarded, and the signal was reconstructed from the relevant components.

For both EMG and IMU signals, Hilbert Transform was applied to extract the signal envelope. This process generates a complex signal with a 90° phase-shifted imaginary component, allowing calculation of a smooth amplitude envelope. Finally, the envelope was further smoothed using a Simple Moving Average (SMA), averaging the signal over a sliding window to produce a cleaner, more exploitable waveform.

C. Feature Extraction

Based on the constructed envelope, the features extracted from the EMG signals were Time difference between the start and end of a peak, Median amplitude of peaks and Average time interval between peaks.

Time difference between the start and end of a peak represents the active phase of the muscle, while Median amplitude of peaks characterizes the power of muscle contractions. Finally, the Average time interval between

peaks corresponds to the interval between each period of muscle activation. The duration of muscle activation is calculated as the difference between the offset time (the instant when muscle activation ends, i.e. the end of the peak) and the onset time (the instant when muscle activation begins, i.e. the start of the peak).

For IMUs, it is important to calculate, in addition to the peaks, the Mean of the Absolute Value (MAV), the Coefficient of Variation (CV) and the Slowness index (η).

Mean of the Absolute Value written in Equation 1 measures the overall intensity of a signal and is particularly useful for assessing bradykinesia in patients with Parkinson's disease.

$$\text{MAV} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |x_i| \quad (1)$$

Where:

N is the total number of signal samples

i is the sample signal

Coefficient of Variation presented in Equation 2 measures the temporal variability between successive cycles.

$$\text{CV} = \frac{\sigma}{\mu} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Where:

σ is the standard deviation of the frequencies

μ is the frequency average

Equation 3 shows the Slowness Index, which indicates how much slower and less fluid the performance of the movement repetitions is.

$$\eta = \frac{1}{N} \cdot \frac{T}{2\pi} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{\langle \dot{y}^2 \rangle}}{\left(\sqrt{\langle (y - \langle y \rangle)^2 \rangle} \right)^2} \quad (3)$$

Where:

T is the time interval

y is the input signal

\dot{y} is the first derivative of y

$\langle \cdot \rangle$ is the mean operator

III. RESULTS

Figures 2, 3, 4 and 5 represent the results of data collection. Each figure presents three situations simulated by the researcher: Healthy, Bradykinesia and Tremor.

Fig. 2. EMG signal during the Finger Tapping task, the signal was collected from the muscle First Dorsal Interosseus in three scenarios: (a) Healthy, (b) Bradykinesia, (c) Tremor.

Fig. 3. EMG signal during the Hand Movement task, which means to open and close the hand, the signal was collected from the muscle Flexor Pollicis Longus in three scenarios: (a) Healthy, (b) Bradykinesia, (c) Tremor.

Features were extracted from each simulated situation, according to Table 1, there were three situations: (i) Healthy, in which the researcher performed the task normally, as a healthy subject; (ii) Bradykinesia, in which the researcher simulated the movements slower and with

decreased amplitude and rhythm; and (iii) Tremor, in which the researcher performed the movements adding a tremor to the hand. The features extracted from the EMG signal during Finger Tapping (FT), Hand Movement (HM) and Flexion and Extension (FE) were the duration of peak, median amplitude and time between peaks.

Table 2 shows the results of the feature extraction from the inertial signals. The smartwatch that contained an accelerometer and a gyroscope was positioned on the wrist of the subject. There is the result of healthy performance (H), of bradykinesia performance (B), and of tremor performance (T). The features extracted from the inertial signals during Pronation and Supination (PS) were the Mean Absolute Value (MAV), the average peaks of amplitude, the coefficient of variation (CV) and the Slowness Index (η).

Fig. 4. EMG signal during the Flexion and Extension task. The signal was collected from the muscle Flexor Digitorum Profundus in three scenarios: (a) Healthy, (b) Bradykinesia, (c) Tremor.

IV. DISCUSSION

Bradykinesia is one of the main motor symptoms of Parkinson's disease, characterized by slowness in the initiation and execution of movements, often with reduced range of motion. Accurate and objective assessment is essential for clinical monitoring, treatment adjustment, and new therapeutic development. This study, part of an internship project, aimed to optimize EMG and IMU sensor placements on a wearable glove for bradykinesia detection during hand movement tasks.

Tasks based on MDS-UPDRS successfully distinguished the three simulated conditions (Healthy, Bradykinesia, Tremor), and the chosen sensor technology proved effective for data collection. Sensor placement was based on anatomical and functional muscle analysis for each task.

Fig. 5. Inertial signal, gyroscope in X axis during the Pronation and Supination task, the signal was collected from a smartwatch on the wrist in three scenarios: (a) Healthy, (b) Bradykinesia, (c) Tremor.

For Finger Tapping, the First Dorsal Interosseus (FDI) and Opponens Pollicis (OP) were targeted due to their role in thumb-index movements. Hand Movement involved the Flexor Digitorum Profundus (FDP) and Flexor Pollicis Longus (FPL), key for flexion and grip. Pronation and Supination relied on IMU data, as EMG signals were minimal for this task. Flexion/Extension primarily engaged the FDP and FPL.

Dry Ag/AgCl electrodes were placed on these muscles, with the best signal-to-noise ratio guiding final placement selection. For flexion/extension, FDP showed the highest amplitude. For hand opening, FPL provided the cleanest signal, while FDI was most reliable for finger tapping.

Feature extraction from EMG showed that bradykinesia simulations produced lower MAV values and peak amplitudes, reflecting reduced muscle contraction intensity. Longer peak intervals indicated slowed activation, and prolonged durations suggested difficulty in maintaining fluid movement, consistent with clinical descriptions of rigidity and slowness in PD patients.

For Pronation/Supination, IMU gyroscope data along the X-axis highlighted reduced rotation speed in bradykinesia. MAV decreased from 2.8 rad/s (Healthy) to 0.4 rad/s (Bradykinesia), and peak amplitudes followed the same trend. Variability (CV) almost doubled, indicating more irregular and less controlled movements.

The η index, a key slowness indicator, also dropped in bradykinesia, confirming slower movement execution. In the Tremor simulation, similar reductions in MAV and η were observed, with unique patterns in peak interval distribution reflecting tremor-related movement disruption.

TABLE 1. EMG features across conditions and muscles

Task	FDI	FPL	FDP	FDI	FPL	FDP	FDI	FPL	FDP	Feature
	Healthy			Brad			Tremor			
FT	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.05	Peak duration (s)
FT	421	25	133	70	25.9	7.49	98	56	54	Median Ampl (μ V)
FT	2.4	2.3	2.9	6.7	8.6	10	13	8.69	9.7	Time between peaks (s)
HM	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.04	Peak duration (s)
HM	75	142	96.6	42	49	11	46.7	72	63	Median Ampl (μ V)
HM	3.72	3.8	5.3	9	6.7	12	9.1	9.9	8.3	Time between peaks (s)
FE	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03	0.04	Peak duration (s)
FE	108	157	615	41	52	26.7	57	69	78	Median Ampl (μ V)
FE	4.9	6.1	5.1	6.3	9.2	6.3	10	8.5	11	Time between peaks (s)

TABLE 2. Kinematic features for Pronation/Supination movement across groups (H = Healthy, B = Brad, T = Tremor)

Axis	MAV			Avg. Amp. Peaks			CV (%)			η		
	H	B	T	H	B	T	H	B	T	H	B	T
Acc X (m^2/s)	0.2	0.2	0.6	5.8	10	12	63.0	139.0	83.0	0.104	0.059	0.091
Acc Y (m^2/s)	2.2	0.7	2.0	3.6	10	13	67.3	75.3	75.8	0.071	0.029	0.051
Acc Z (m^2/s)	3.9	0.8	1.6	3.3	13	8.6	49.6	135.0	65.9	0.069	0.016	0.034
Gyr X (rad/s)	2.8	0.4	1.5	3.7	11	7.9	52.7	96.8	79.6	0.061	0.015	0.044
Gyr Y (rad/s)	0.3	0.06	0.3	3.9	7.3	8.8	52.5	139.0	95.7	0.071	0.024	0.034
Gyr Z (rad/s)	0.1	0.05	0.1	4.7	5.7	12.0	76.7	230.0	61.3	0.057	0.030	0.038

Overall, the analysis of MAV, CV, and η across EMG and IMU signals effectively differentiated bradykinesia from healthy and tremor-like movements. These findings validate the chosen sensor placements and confirm the glove’s potential for objective bradykinesia assessment.

V. CONCLUSION

This study proposed and tested optimal sensor placements for Electromyography (EMG) and Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) sensors on a wearable glove, evaluating their effectiveness in detecting bradykinesia and tremor during hand movement tasks. The combined analysis of three key parameters, Mean Absolute Value (MAV), Coefficient of Variation (CV), and η index, proved effective in differentiating bradykinesia and tremor from healthy movement patterns within the tested protocol. These findings highlight the potential of this sensor configuration for objective and quantitative assessment of bradykinesia and tremor in Parkinson’s disease.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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